

Bibliometric Analysis of the Literature on Organizational Readiness: Mapping and Direction

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ABSTRACT: The COVID-19 pandemic is mostly responsible for the decline in business financial performance. It is believed that the company's survival is contingent upon the organization's readiness to integrate digital technology at the operational and strategic levels. Despite the abundance of literature in this field, there has been no empirical research to characterize previous studies or provide guidance for future studies that have a significant impact. Therefore, we have designed this investigation to fill this gap. The bibliometric analysis method employed in the research involves the initial step of conducting a search of the Scopus-indexed journal database using the title, abstract, and keywords "organizational readiness", "readiness to change", "digital maturity" or "digital capability". We selected a total of 3528 articles from a pool of 93,307 by applying filters based on specific topics and time periods. Following this, we compiled the meta data using the Publish and Perish (PoP) program and generated research trend visualizations using Vosviewer. The research findings indicate that Parida, V., a Swedish writer, is the most productive. However, we discovered that the authors who published the most impactful articles were not necessarily the most prolific authors or countries. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, research on organizational readiness that can assist small and medium-sized businesses in gaining a competitive advantage and enhancing their value could be the next area of investigation.

KEYWORDS: Bibliometric Analysis, Future Direction, Maturity, Organizational Readiness, VosViewer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a significant increase in the use of digital technology in society [1]. Video conferencing platforms like Zoom and Google Meet have become more prevalent in the education sector. Meanwhile, e-commerce platforms have surged in the business and economic sectors [2]. Furthermore, digitalization is improving the efficiency of supply chain processes [3]. Mobile technology, cloud computing, data mining and analytics, and big data to enhance work and organization are also increasing [4]. It seems that the business's ability to embrace digital technologies and transition from a traditional business to a digital-based approach will be critical for its survival [5].

In this study, organizational readiness is an assessment of an organization's ability to implement changes or enhancements to its business processes by integrating IT infrastructure, utilizing human resources, designing digital strategies, and altering organizational culture in a digital-based context [6]–[9]. Several studies have examined organizational readiness, which is often referred to as organizational IT readiness [10], digital capability [11], [12] or digital maturity [2], [5], [8], [13]. Maturity and readiness are both synonymous and possess comparable attributes [14], [15]. A wide range of investigations have concentrated on organizational readiness. Organizational readiness has an impact on firm performance [16]–[19], organizational capability [20]–[23], and other associated factors.

However, no bibliometric analysis has been conducted to map the existing literature. Thus, the objective of the study is to fill that gap. Organizational readiness plays a crucial role in its ability to undertake digital transformation. Researchers need to have a thorough understanding of current research in their area of interest [24]. Utilizing bibliometrics, researchers have the ability to direct future research endeavors and foster global collaboration. This study uses bibliometric analysis to examine current research trends and identify the potential for future research on organizational readiness.

II. METHODS

This study employs a bibliometric methodology to conduct a literature review. A literature review is a systematic analysis of existing research to evaluate and analyze a specific study domain while also providing a rationale for the aims, hypotheses, and research questions [25]. Bibliometric analysis is a research method that uses the social, intellectual, and conceptual framework of

scientific disciplines to investigate the development of a research field encompassing subjects and authors [26]. Bibliometric analysis is a commonly employed method in academia that involves quantitatively studying papers, books, journals, and other forms of written communication [27]. We use the bibliometric analysis framework, as proposed by Sifa [28], in this study. Figure 1 shows the research methodology.

Figure 1. Research design

The following steps outline the stages of bibliometric research needed to conduct an analysis. Initially, we commence a thorough investigation. We performed a comprehensive search of existing literature in the Scopus indexed journal database using the title, abstract, and keywords "organizational readiness," "readiness to change," "digital maturity," or "digital capability." Between 1964 and 2024, the population had 93,307 articles.

We conducted data extraction by narrowing down the search using specific criteria such as publication year, document type, language, and subject area. Our study focuses only on the disciplines of business, management, and accounting. The selected sample from 2014–2024 consisted of 3528 articles. We used the indexed-Scopus database for data collection because of its public accessibility and widespread use in scientific research.

Next, we will process the metadata using Vosviewer and Publish or Perish (PoP) to answer research questions. Vosviewer is a free software program that allows us to create visualization maps from network data. It can take the form of interconnections between researcher profiles in one or multiple fields, countries, topics, research areas, keywords, and sources [29]. Additionally, bibliometric analysis can evaluate the productivity and impact of each research variable in a study [28].

We looked at the following indicators as part of this study: author, journal, article, and country. Additionally, this investigation employs citation analysis to assess critical elements that have an impact. One of the bibliographic reference methods, citation analysis [30], captures relationships between studies and determines the impact of research [31]. Finally, network analysis is conducted to evaluate current research trends and map future research potential.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An overview of the research data can be seen in Table 1.

Table I. Citation Metrics

Metrics	Data
Publication year	2014-2024
Citation year	10 (2014-2024)
Papers	3.528
Citations	83.301
Cites/year	8.330,1
Cites/paper	23,61
Cites/author	32.469,96
Papers/author	1.428,44
Author/paper	3,17
h-index	129
g-index	203

There are 3.528 articles selected from 160 journals over a ten-year period. This data demonstrates the significant journal specialization and the productivity of publishing articles on this subject. This suggests that the topic of "organizational readiness" is highly relevant and captivating enough to warrant further investigation.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of publications over a span of 10 years. Each year, the number of publications increases, and 2023 will record the most (768 articles). The number of citations directly correlates with the outcome. In 2023, there will be a peak of citations with the largest impact, reaching a total of 26,411. In 2024, there will be a decline in the quantity of citations and documents. Researchers suspect this decline is due to the fact that this study only collected data up until July 2024. Results in 2024 can still change, and they have the potential to increase.

Figure 2. Annual distribution of organizational readiness article

A. The Productive Authors

According to our analysis, Parida, V., from Luleå University of Technology, is the most frequent author. The author has contributed to a total of 19 articles, either as the first, second, or third author. These articles were published over a decade. The details of the article by Parida, V., are as follows: one article in 2015 and 2018, two articles in 2019 and 2020, three articles in 2021, two articles in 2022, and four articles in 2023 and 2024. The article titled "How entrepreneurial SMEs compete through digital

platforms: The roles of digital platform capability, network capability, and ambidexterity" has received the highest number of citations, with a total of 413 citations, making it the most significant article. The top-ranked article has the greatest number of citations and explores the ways in which digital platform capabilities might enhance the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This research is among the limited number of empirical studies that investigate this particular subject.

Table II. The most frequent organizational readiness papers

No	Author	Country	TP	TC	C/P
1	Parida, V.	Swedia, Finlandia	19	2.232	117,47
2	Gupta, S.	Prancis	14	1.004	71,71
3	Kraus, S.	Italia	14	1.188	84,86
4	Chatterjee, S.	India	12	543	45,25
5	Suresh, M.	India	12	441	36,75
6	Vrontis, D.	Yunani	12	305	25,42
7	Antony, J.	UEA	11	285	25,91
8	Dwivedi, Y.K.	UK	11	1.873	170,27
9	Garza-Reyes, J.A.	UK	11	491	44,64
10	Belhadi, A.	Maroko	10	349	34,90

TP: Total Publication; TC: Total Citation; C/P: Average Citation per Publication

Based on the data, Parida, V., is not only the most productive writer when it comes to publishing papers, but she also holds the top spot in terms of having the highest number of citations. Parida, V., authored and published a collection of 19 publications, which have collectively garnered a total of 2,232 citations. Dwivedi and YK come in second. Despite having fewer publications than Gupta, S., and Kraus, S., the number of citations exceeds that of these two authors, with a total of 1,873 and an average citation value per publication (C/P) of 170.27.

Figure 3. Co-authorship

We used bibliometric analysis to describe a collaborative relationship between authors. According to Figure 3, Gupta, S., achieved the greatest collaborative relationship strength value of 19 link strength (LS). Gupta, S., nearly linked the entire study group. This indicates that his research established many co-authorship links and indirectly influenced research in the organizational readiness literature.

B. The Productive Journals

For this study, we used 3528 articles from 160 journals as a sample. Then we examined the top ten ranked journals. According to the data in Table 3, the journal Technological Forecasting and Social Change had the highest number of publications, with a total of 121 documents. Figure 4 presents data that highlights the remarkable consistency of the Technological Forecasting and Social Change journal in its annual publication of articles, outperforming other journals in this regard.

Table III. The most frequent organizational readiness journals

No	Source	Publisher	TP	Cite Score	SJR	SNIP
1	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Elsevier Ltd.	121	21,3	2.232	117,47
2	IEEE Transactions On Engineering Management	IEEE Inc.	76	10,3	1.004	71,71
3	Journal of Cleaner Production	Elsevier Ltd.	71	20,4	1.188	84,86
4	Journal of Business Research	Elsevier Inc.	60	20,3	543	45,25
5	International Journal of Production Research	Taylor & Francis Ltd.	42	19,2	441	36,75
6	Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management	Emerald Ltd.	42	16,3	305	25,42
7	International Journal of Production Economics	Elsevier B.V.	41	21,4	285	25,91
8	Technology in Society	Emerald Ltd.	38	17,9	1.873	170,27
9	European Journal of Innovation Management	Emerald Ltd.	34	10,4	491	44,64
10	International Journal of Information Management	Elsevier Ltd.	34	53,1	349	34,90

TP: Total Publication; TC: Total Citation; C/P: Average Citation per Publication

Figure 4. The distribution of the most frequent journals

Scopus-indexed journals use two indicators, namely SJR (SCImago Journal Rank) and SNIP (Source Normalized Impact per Paper), to evaluate impact factors. The SJR indicator consider the credibility of the journal that cites the research. We adjust the weight of the citations based on whether they originate from a high- or low-status journal [32]. Meanwhile, the SNIP indicator looks at multiple factors, including the citation rate per paper, the amount of indexed literature, and the publication speed. Table 3

demonstrates that Elsevier Ltd.'s International Journal of Information Management is the most recognized journal. This conclusion is based on its exceptional citation, SJR, and SNIP scores, which reached impressive values of 53.1, 5,775, and 5,825, respectively.

Finally, we conducted an analysis of the bibliographical coupling network. Initially, we set a threshold of 5. Nevertheless, the findings showed a significant degree of variability and complexity, resulting in a notably low level of readability. We then increased the criteria for the minimum number of documents to 15 and set a higher threshold of 50 citations. Thus, our research generated five distinct groups, as illustrated in Figure 5. According to the findings presented in Figure 5, Technological Forecasting and Social Change emerges as the most productive journal, boasting the highest publication frequency and the strongest connections with other journals (link strength = 51,356). It is important to note that these conclusions are based on the sample used in this study.

Figure 5. Bibliographical coupling of sources

C. The Productive Country

Given the results of the collected samples, a total of 116 countries have made significant contributions to the current repository of literature on organizational readiness. Table 4 presents our summary of the top 10 countries in our study.

Table IV. Countries researched in organizational readiness

No	Country	TP	TC	C/P	h	g
1	United States	464	19.596	42,23	64	131
2	United Kingdom	429	15.938	37,15	65	114
3	China	423	7.489	17,70	45	74
4	India	317	7.736	24,40	42	81
5	Australia	223	5.925	26,57	38	71
6	German	214	8.681	40,57	42	90
7	Italy	206	7.684	37,30	45	83
8	Indonesia	191	1.170	6,13	18	27
9	France	153	7.845	51,27	37	87
10	Malaysia	141	2.566	18,20	24	48

TP: Total Publication; TC: Total Citation;
C/P: Average Citation per Publication; h: h-index; g: g-index

The United States is the leading country in terms of publications, with a total of 464 articles. The following table presents the distribution of publications and citations: In 2014, there were 17 publications that received a total of 9 citations. In 2015, there were 21 publications with a total of 41 citations. The following year, in 2016, there were 18 publications that garnered 131 citations. Moving on to 2017, there were 25 publications that received 179 citations. The trend continued in 2018 with 35 publications and 410 citations. In 2019, there were 38 publications that received a significant boost in citations, totaling 768. The year 2020 saw a further increase, with 43 publications and 1,359 citations. The upward trajectory continued in 2021 with 59 publications and 2,310 citations. In 2022, there were 73 publications that received 3,650 citations. The following year, in 2023, the number of publications remained the same, but the citations increased to 5,841. Finally, by the year 2024, there were 62 publications that received a total of 4,891 citations.

Typically, there is no direct correlation between the quantity of documents and the number of citations (C/P). It is evident that certain documents still lack citations and have failed to make a significant impact on the existing body of literature. Indonesia has achieved an impressive ranking in the top 10, with a remarkable 153 documents and an impressive 1,170 citations. The results of this study suggest that researchers from Indonesia have demonstrated a high level of productivity in publishing academic works related to organizational readiness. Nevertheless, the value of C/P in documents generated by Indonesian researchers remains lower compared to researchers from other countries in the top 10 rankings. Collaboration and co-authorship play a crucial role in broadening the impact of publications by Indonesian authors.

D. The Impactful Articles

Through a comprehensive citation analysis of the entire sample, we sought to identify the articles with the highest impact. Table 5 presents a concise overview of the top 10 articles. We came across a scholarly article titled "*Digital Transformation: A Multidisciplinary Reflection and Research Agenda*" by Verhoef et al. [33]. During that period, inadequate amounts of empirical research spanning multiple disciplines existed, leaving digital transformation largely unexplored. Hence, this study has the capacity to address current knowledge gaps and yield numerous insightful findings. The average number of citations per year for this article is 564.33. We cannot overstate the significance of this article in shaping the literature field. Ding and Cronin [34] define popularity in their study as the frequency with which other scholarly articles reference a corresponding author. According to the provided definition, the findings of this study lead to the conclusion that Verhoef et al. [33] are the most widely recognized authors in the field of organizational readiness.

In our study, we applied bibliographic coupling analysis to identify the key items within our dataset (Sifa, 2022). We commonly use this method to automatically cluster extensive datasets. This grouping enables the identification of two documents within a single publication, each referencing research by a common third author. The colors in Figure 5 represent the different groups of articles as depicted by the authors.

We set a threshold of 80 as the minimum number of citations. As a result, we have identified eight sets, each containing 288 documents, all of which meet the specified threshold. Our study's findings reveal that Warner and Soluk's articles from the Red Group have emerged as the most frequently co-cited documents. These articles achieved a significant total link strength (LS) of 436 and 386, respectively. Among the 288 documents, the researchers exhibit a strong correlation with the other 10 groups.

Table V. The impactful articles

No	Author	Title	Year	C	C/Y
1	P.C. Verhoef, T.Broekhuizen Y.Bart, A.Bhattacharya, J. Qi Dong, N. Fabian, M. Haenlein	Digital Transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda	2021	1.693	564,3
2	K.S.R. Warner, M. Wäger	Building dynamic capabilities for digital transformation: An ongoing process of strategic renewal	2019	1.181	236,2
3	Y.K. Dwivedi, N. Kshetri, L. Hughes	So what if ChatGPT wrote it?" Multidisciplinary perspective on opportunities, challenges and implications of generative conversational AI for research practice and policy	2023	979	979

No	Author	Title	Year	C	C/Y
4	J. Van Doorn, M. Mende, S.M. Noble, J. Hulland, A.L. Ostrom	Domo Arigato Mr Roboto: Emergence of Automated Social Presence in Organizational Frontlines and Customers' Service Experiences	2017	771	110,1
5	A.Parasuraman, C.L. Colby	An updated and streamlined Technology Readiness Index: TRI 2.0	2015	751	83,4
6	H. Gangwar, H. Date, R. Ramaswamy	Understanding determinants of cloud computing adoption using an integrated TAM-TOE model	2015	684	76
7	L. Li	China's manufacturing locus in 2025: With a comparison of "Made-in-China 2025" and "Industry 4.0"	2018	677	112,8
8	F.Svahn, L. Mathiassen, R. Lindgren	Embracing digital innovation in incumbent firms: How Volvo Cars managed competing concerns	2017	580	82,9
9	M. Rchinger, R. Rauter, C. Müller, W. Vorraber, E. Schirgi	Digitalization and its influence on business model innovation	2019	552	110,4
10	C.E. Helfat, R.S. Raubitschek	Dynamic and integrative, capabilities for profiting from innovation in digital platform-based ecosystems	2018	532	88,7

C: Citation; C/Y: Citation per year

Figure 6. Bibliographical coupling of documents

E. Top Frequent Author's Keywords: Mapping and direction

We used co-occurrence analysis in our study to explore the frequently discussed keywords in the literature on organizational readiness. Co-occurrences are observed when two keywords are found together within a keyword article, indicating a correlation between the two concepts [35]. We defined a threshold of twenty-five as the minimum number of occurrences. The notable size of the database and the need to eliminate unrelated keywords led us to choose this approach. Our analysis revealed that out of a total of 9677 keywords, 7 groups consisting of 67 keywords each met the threshold. Figure 7 illustrates this discovery.

Figure 7. Bibliographical coupling of author’s keyword

Co-occurrence analysis is a valuable tool for gaining insights into significant research findings across the global literature. In the network, the keyword "digital transformation" stands out as the largest node, with 431 occurrences and a total link strength of 552. Table 6 displays the nine other keywords that follow.

Table VI. The analysis of co-occurrence of keyword

No	Keyword	Occurrence	Total Link Strength
1	Industry 4.0	216	302
2	Dynamic capabilities	194	288
3	Digitalization	170	231
4	Innovation	130	200
5	SMES	104	155
6	Artificial intelligence	105	138
7	Sustainability	87	138
8	Digital technologies	61	94
9	Business model innovation	55	92

Figure 8. Overlay visualization of co-occurrence of keyword

Future research can search for smaller nodes that remain connected to the main research or have not yet established direct connections within the network. We uncovered several insights that could guide future research directions. We have established the relationship between organizational readiness, digital transformation, innovation, firm performance, dynamic capabilities, and digital technologies like artificial intelligence in small and medium companies. Hence, it will introduce novel perspectives to the future research agenda. During our observations, we carefully examined the movement in the organizational readiness literature. Figure 8 depicts the visualization during the observation period.

Scientists have examined literature from the outset of the period, focusing on overarching themes such as change management, organizational change, strategy, digitization, information technology, leadership, and knowledge management. During the middle period, there was a notable surge in literature focused on various topics such as digitalization, industry 4.0, digital economy, business model innovation, maturity model, capabilities, sustainability, supply chain, and digital innovation. Recent literature has seen a significant growth in the discussion of various topics such as digital transformation, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, resilience, dynamic capabilities, digital leadership, competitive advantage, and value co-creation. These subjects have emerged as crucial global agenda items in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The focus of the study is on small and medium-sized enterprises. Indonesian researchers face a significant challenge in bridging the existing gap in scientific literature. They aim to stay up-to-date with the latest research trends and contribute new insights through their analysis.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed metadata from 3,528 articles from various regions, focusing on the title, abstract, and specific keywords related to organizational readiness, readiness to change, digital maturity, and digital capability. Through our research, we have discovered a correlation between author productivity and impact. Interestingly, we observed that the least productive authors were often the most impactful. This finding suggests that there may not be a strong connection between collaboration among authors and their overall impact. Furthermore, we observed varying outcomes in the journals with the highest productivity and those that published the most notable articles. The United States is actively conducting research and publishing articles in this particular field. Our study revealed that Verhoef et al. [36] authored "Digital Transformation: A Multidisciplinary Reflection and Research Agenda", the article with the highest impact in terms of citations.

Furthermore, digital transformation is currently the most frequently discussed topic. Thus, it is important for future studies to investigate keywords that have a low frequency of occurrence. The overlay visualization we have developed further confirms our

findings that the most recent trends revolve around digital technologies, artificial intelligence, resilience, dynamic capabilities, digital leadership, competitive advantage, and value co-creation.

Hence, we propose that future studies explore new trends in the field of organizational readiness, specifically focusing on its potential to generate value and provide an advantage to small and medium-sized enterprises in the post-Covid-19 era. The author views this theme as highly relevant in the future, given its close connection to company performance, competitive advantage, and value co-creation. We also expect these factors to directly improve employee welfare.

The relationship between organizational readiness and digital leadership has been the subject of limited research within this network. In addition to this, the concept of sustainability holds enormous significance as a subject of study and has emerged as a global priority. The potential for collaboration between the mentioned elements holds promise for future advancements.

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Cite this Article: Zahwa Fitria Gumilang, Budhi Prihartono (2024). Bibliometric Analysis of the Literature on Organizational Readiness: Mapping and Direction. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(7), 5801-5812